

Interaction of Thionyl Chloride with Substances Containing the Reactive Methylene Group. Part V.

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A study of the interaction of thionyl chloride on substances containing the reactive methylene group (Naik and Parekh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 137) showed that sulphoxides of the general formula $R'NH'CO'C : SO'CO'NHR$ are formed, which by the further reducing action of thionyl chloride condense to form sulphides, $[(R'NHCO)_2C : S : C(R'NHCO)_2]$. Naik and Thosar (*ibid.*, 1932, **9**, 127) investigated this reaction further and obtained sulphides of the type

from the substituted amides of malonic acid and acetoacetic acid, and sulphides of the type $CONHR'C : S'COOC_2H_5$ from the amates of these acids.

It was observed during these investigations that the presence of foreign substances in the reaction mixture affected the course of the reaction to a very great extent. It was, therefore, thought interesting to examine the effects of catalysts on this reaction and in the present work finely divided copper was used as a catalyst.

When copper was used as a catalyst in the interaction between thionyl chloride and malondiphenylamide, the following substance was obtained : $(C_6H_5 NH'CO)_2 C : S$.

Michaelis and Philips (*Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 559), who obtained a sulphide by the action of thionyl chloride on acetoacetic ester, assumed that thionyl chloride behaves as if it were a mixture of sulphur dichloride and sulphuryl chloride.

We do not find support for this view of the reaction because if sulphuryl chloride is formed, it would, in all probability, have acted on some of the amide and given rise to chloro-compounds (*cf.* Naik and Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 11). In all probability the thionyl chloride decomposes in presence of copper into SCl_2 , SO_2 and copper chloride (as with other metals, *vide* Mellor, 'Comprehensive

Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry," Vol. X, p. 662). This view finds further support in the fact that when the used-up catalyst is lixiviated with water, a green solution, showing the presence of copper chloride, is obtained and that sulphur dioxide can be detected in the gaseous products of the reaction. The reaction may be represented thus :—

The above constitution has been assigned to these compounds from the following considerations :—

(i) Acetoacetic ester, which does not contain a phenyl group, reacts with thionyl chloride to form a sulphide which shows that the hydrogen atoms attacked are those of the reactive methylene group and neither those of the phenyl group nor those of the -NHR group (Michaelis and Philips, *loc. cit.*).

(ii) On reduction with alkaline hydrosulphide, the original amide is obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Interaction of Malondiphenylamide with Thionyl Chloride.—Thionyl chloride (2.5 g.) was added to malondiphenylamide (2.5 g.) in dry benzene (30 c.c.) containing copper powder (1 g.). Gases were evolved and soon the mixture turned red. After $\frac{1}{2}$ hour the mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hours, filtered hot and the cold solution dropped slowly into a large amount of dry petroleum with constant stirring. A compound was precipitated which was reprecipitated from benzene and petroleum 3 or 4 times, m.p. 105.6°, with previous shrinking at 80°. It is soluble in benzene, slightly so in carbon disulphide and insoluble in petroleum. (Found : N, 9.58; S, 11.41. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 9.85; S, 11.26 per cent).

Hydrolysis with Water.—The above compound (2 g.) was heated with 20 c.c. of distilled water for 30 minutes. The paste formed was taken out and the water filtered off hot, when on cooling a crystalline substance was obtained. This was collected and recrystallised from alcohol and was found to be the original amide, m.p. 225-26°. The paste was treated with carbon disulphide and on evaporation of the disulphide, free sulphur was left behind.

Reduction by Alkaline Hydrosulphide.—The substance (5 g.) was refluxed for about an hour with 50 c.c. of alcohol. An aqueous solution of sodium hydrosulphide (prepared by saturating 1.5 g. of caustic soda with hydrogen sulphide in a small quantity of water) and caustic soda (5.7 g. dissolved in a small quantity of water) was gradually added to it, when a brown solution was obtained, which was diluted with a large quantity of water when precipitation occurred. The precipitate was collected and washed free from alkali by hot water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 224-25°. It was malon-anilide.

Hydrolysis by Caustic Potash.—The compound (5 g.) was refluxed for 2 hours with a solution of caustic potash (10 g. in 16 c.c. of water) and the cold solution diluted with water and extracted with ether. On evaporating the ether the oily liquid was found to be aniline. The residue was treated with hydrochloric acid, when hydrogen sulphide was found to evolve.

The other compounds were prepared in the same way and the following table summarises the properties of the compounds obtained from the different amides.

Amides.	M. p.	Shrinks at.	Formulae.	Analysis.	
				Found.	Calc.
Malondiphenylamide	105°	80°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	S, 11.41 N, 9.53	11.26 9.55
Malondi- <i>o</i> -tolylamide	138°	110°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	S, 10.63	10.25
Malondi- <i>p</i> -tolylamide	108°	60°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	S, 10.30 N, 8.76	10.25 8.97
Malondi- <i>m</i> -tolylamide	114°	60°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	S, 10.33	10.25
Malondi- α -naphthylamide	168°		C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.83	8.33
Malondixylidide (1:3:4)	126°	95°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.03	9.41
Malondixylidide (1:4:5)	146°	100°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.21	9.41

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